

Synthesis of Some Fused 2-Arylimidazoles and their Derivatives

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The synthesis of several fused 2-arylimidazoles, 1-hydroxy-2-arylimidazole-3-oxides, 1-hydroxy-2-arylimidazoles starting from 2-arylimino-3-aryl-1, 3-thiazolidine-4, 5-diones(I) 4H-thiazolo (2,1-b) imidazole-2, 3-dione (II), 1,4-benzothiazin-2, 3-dione(III), phanquone (IV), acenaphthenequinone, furil, phenanthraquinone have been described. Few imidazoles gave coloured dimeric products (VIII, IX & X) on oxidation with hexacyanoferrate. Their structures have been confirmed by elemental analysis and IR spectra.

BENZIMIDAZOLE derivatives have been reported to possess significant bactericidal¹, fungicidal² and tuberculostatic³ properties. Besides MAO inhibitory effects are also associated with certain derivatives of benzimidazole^{4,5}. Very recently their potential anti-trypanosomal⁶, antiviral⁷ and antiestrogenic⁸ activities also have been evaluated. In this paper we report the synthesis of some of these compounds, with a view to explore their potential pharmacological properties.

In the present work the earlier method of Steck and Day⁹ was employed for the preparation of 2-arylimidazoles. The reaction involves the direct condensation of 1,2-diketones with appropriate aldehydes in refluxing glacial acetic acid containing excess ammonium acetate. The process is believed to take place via an unstable diimine intermediate of the diketone. Simultaneous attack of this transient species on the aldehyde carbonyl followed by ready loss of elements of water gives the isoimidazole which undergoes a rapid 1,5-hydrogen shift (Scheme-1).

Scheme 1

The diketones like acenaphthenequinone and furil were prepared following the available literature procedure^{10,11}. 2-imino-1,3-thiazolidine-4,5-diones(I) were prepared¹² from 1,3-diaryl thioureas and oxalyl chloride in good yield. The synthetic thiourea derivatives were treated with oxalyl chloride (Riedel) in

1,2-dichloro ethane with external cooling followed by heating at 85° for 0.5 hr. As expected the reactions of oxalyl chloride with 2-amino thiazole and *o*-amino thiophenol gave the diketones II and III respectively in appreciable yields (Chart-1). All of them gave bands around 1550, 1490 and 1450 cm⁻¹ characteristic of imidazole system (ref. 13).

Chart 1

I = R = R₁ = Phenyl
I(A) = R = R₁ = *p*-chloro phenyl
I(B) = R = R₁ = *o*-bromo phenyl

1-hydroxy-imidazoles have a broad spectrum of biological activity¹⁴ and can be conveniently prepared by the ammoniacal condensation of dionemoximes with aldehydes^{15,16}. Akagane and Allan¹⁷ reported

Scheme 2

R = Me, Ph, Pyrid-2-yl.

the new flexible one step method for their synthesis starting from 1,2-diketones. These authors have condensed only the single diketone biacetyl with aldehydes like acetaldehyde, benzaldehyde and pyridine- α -aldehyde (Scheme-2).

TABLE 1*—PHYSICAL DATA ON IMIDAZOLE DERIVATIVES

Diketone	Aldehyde	m.p. in °C	Yield %	Colour
I	a	261	34	Dirty brown
	b	219	35	Yellow
	c	212	43	Pale yellow
	d	231	40	Yellow
I(A)	a	282	13	Brown
	b	238	16	Dull yellow
	c	151	18	Greenish yellow
	d	247	10	Brown
I(B)	a	178	92	Brownish black
	b	105	60	Colourless
	c	187	50	Yellow
	d	143	48	Brown
II	a	320	30	Black
	b	56	25	Brown
	c	108	35	Brown
	d	62	32	Brownish black
III	a	205	45	Brown
	b	200	42	Yellow
	c	175	48	Yellow
	d	212	55	Reddish brown
IV	a	208	22	Brownish black
	b	148	94	Dirty yellow
	c	194	53	Pale yellow
	d	63	40	Yellow
	f	168	40	Brown
Acenaphthene quinone	i	305	40	Brownish black
	a	202	28.4	Black
	b	110	30	Reddish brown
	c	122	75.5	Brown
	d	50	69	Red
Furil	e	94	52	Brown
	a	142	30	Dirty brown
	b	190	25	Yellow

Table 1*—(Contd.)

Diketone	Aldehyde	m.p. in °C	Yield %	Colour
Phenathraquinone	c	161	21	Pale brown
	d	130	35	Brown
	a	165	77	Black
	d	128	63	Brown
	e	204	14	Pale brown
	f	245	33	Yellowish brown
	g	265	31	Brownish yellow
	h	146	49	Black

a = Furfural, b = Benzaldehyde, c = *p*-chloro benzaldehyde, d = *p*-dimethyl amino benzaldehyde, e = *p*-bromo benzaldehyde, f = thiophene aldehyde, g = anisaldehyde, h = pyridine-2-aldehyde, i = 5-bromo indole-3-carboxylic aldehyde, * C,H,N analyses are within $\pm 0.4\%$.

This novel approach prompted us to synthesize some more 1-hydroxy-imidazole-3-oxides starting from various diketones. All the diketones in our observation gave solid crystalline compounds except furil which surprisingly gave only liquid products. The IR spectra of all these compounds reveal a peak around 1230 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of N-oxide group. The poor yields encountered in these reactions could be explained in terms of the formation of some insoluble intermediate side product which sometimes precipitate out in the reaction vessel. The dioxime behaviour of these systems was tentatively confirmed by the formation of various complex compound with transition divalent metal ions like Cu_{II} , Co_{II} , Ni_{II} etc. The physical data of imidazole oxides are summarised in Table-2.

TABLE 2*—PHYSICAL DATA ON 1-HYDROXY-IMIDAZOLE-3-OXIDES.

Diketone	Aldehyde	m.p. in °C	Yield %	Colour
I	a	202	13	Brown
	b	134	10	Brownish yellow
	c	98	12	Red
	d	108	33	Orange yellow
I(A)	a	129	22	Brown
	b	174	21	Brownish yellow
	c	132	26	Reddish brown
	d	98	30	Brown
I(B)	a	126	37	Brown
	b	155	15	Brown
	c	142	14	Reddish white
	d	94	17	Brown

Table 2*—(Contd.)

Diketone	Aldehyde	m.p. in °C	Yield %	Colour
II	a	158	32	Pale yellow
	c	82	32	Yellowish
	d	94	31	Colourless
III	a	159	20	Orange
	b	174	40	Yellow
	c	140	49	Yellow
	d	130	75	Pale yellow
IV	a	92	31.7	Colourless
	c	107	35	Green
	d	125	32	Brownish pink
Acenaphthene quinone	a	176	41.5	Pale yellow
	b	185	56	Buff
	c	175	72	Yellow
	d	118	70	Brown

a=Furfural, b=Benzaldehyde, c=*p*-chloro-benzaldehyde, d=*p*-dimethyl aminobenzaldehyde
 * C, H, N, analyses are within $\pm 0.4\%$.

It is reported¹⁷ that 1-hydroxy-imidazole-3-oxides are stable entities, easily reducible to the corresponding 1-hydroxy imidazoles by sodium boro hydride. This observation is very much analogous to the currently well documented deoxygenation reactions encountered with triphenylphosphine and trialkylphosphites. Higher temperature can affect further reduction. The physical properties of 1-hydroxy-imidazoles of acenaphthene-quinone and phanquone are reported in Table-3. Their gross structures are established to be V and VI on the basis of analyses (Chart-2). The IR spectra of these compounds show the absence of the N-oxide band as compared to their precursors.

TABLE 3*—PHYSICAL DATA ON 1-HYDROXY-IMIDAZOLES

Com- pound	Nature of R	m.p. in °C	Yield %	Colour
V	Furyl	112	40	Brown
	Phenyl	70	54	Brownish red
	<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	167	50	Green
VI	<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	109	82	Yellow
	<i>p</i> -dimethyl aminophenyl	114	70	Orange

* C, H, N analyses are within $\pm 0.4\%$.

Chart 2

Hayashi and Maeda¹⁸ have reported the oxidation of 2,4,5-triphenyl-imidazole to dimeric product VII presumably going through a 2,4,5-triphenyl-imidazolyl radical (Chart-3).

Chart 3

The dimer also can be generated conveniently by oxidation with hexacyanoferrate¹⁹. The structures of

Chart 4

R = Furyl, Phenyl, *p*-Chlorophenyl, *p*-Dimethyl amino phenyl.

the dimers were confirmed by extensive NMR and UV studies. The imidazoles obtained from acenaphthenequinone and phanquone with diverse aromatic aldehydes in the conditions of above set of reactions gave the expected dimers. Imidazoles of 2-arylimino-3-aryl-1,3-thiazolidine-4,5-diones also gave the dimers having comparatively low melting points. They have been assigned the structures VIII, IX, X compatible with the spectral data (Chart-4).

These timely observation further substantiates that the formation of a dimer of structural type VII is a general one in case of 2-substituted condensed imidazoles. All of them are coloured and the observed yields are generally poor. Many of these compounds show chromotropic properties. The physical properties of these compounds are shown in Table-4.

(0.7 g, 0.005 mole) for 1 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled, diluted with water (50 ml) and neutralised with liquor ammonia. The crude imidazole was collected and crystallised from absolute alcohol to give a crystalline pale yellow compound, m.p. 194°, yield 0.87 g (53%). IR : ν_{max} (Nujol) (cm^{-1}) : 3400, 1670, 1570, 1450.

Preparation of 1-hydroxy-2-p-chlorophenylimidazole-3-oxide from phanquone :

A solution of phanquone (1.05 g, 0.005 mole) and *p*-chloro benzaldehyde (0.7 g, 0.005 mole) in methanol (40 ml) was treated with hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.7 g, 0.01 mole). The mixture was stirred at ambient temperature for 20 hr, neutralised with solid sodium carbonate and filtered. Concentration of the filtrate under reduced pressure gave a residue which was

TABLE 4—PHYSICAL DATA ON IMIDAZOLE DIMERS

Compound (Dimer)	Nature of R	m.p. in °C	Yield %	Colour	C, H and N analysis					
					Found			Calculated		
					C	H	N	C	H	N
VIII	Furyl	298	15	Brownish black	79.92	3.80	10.92	79.80	3.68	10.80
	Phenyl	202	21	Brown	83.86	4.82	11.70	83.71	4.74	11.54
	<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	125	26	Reddish brown	78.40	4.56	10.88	78.26	4.61	10.76
	<i>p</i> -dimethyl aminophenyl	238	17	Bright red	81.34	5.25	13.62	81.29	5.16	13.54
IX	Furyl	208	7	Brown	72.14	2.60	19.65	72.08	2.47	19.78
	Phenyl	184	9.5	Pale orange	75.30	4.10	20.86	75.19	3.90	20.00
	<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	348	19	Pale orange	67.02	3.25	18.58	66.83	3.13	18.45
	<i>p</i> -dimethyl aminophenyl	271	7	Bright red	76.25	4.01	20.12	76.19	3.96	20.00
X	Furyl	76	15	Brown	65.98	3.82	15.80	65.82	3.64	15.68
	Phenyl	73	17	Brownish black	72.10	3.90	15.42	71.83	4.07	15.25
	<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	68	22	Orange	72.24	3.65	12.85	72.30	3.49	13.71
	<i>p</i> -dimethyl aminophenyl	77	10	Brown	70.36	4.98	16.90	70.24	4.87	17.07

The compounds are under active examination for their potential pharmacological properties against various microorganisms.

Experimental

Melting points are determined in open capillaries in a (WISWO) melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra are recorded on a Perkin-Elmer-137 spectrophotometer.

Synthesis of 2-p-chlorophenylphanquimidazole (IV C) :

A solution of phanquone IV (1.05 g, 0.005 mole), ammonium acetate (0.77 g, 0.01 mole) in hot glacial acetic acid (5ml) was refluxed with *p*-chloro benzaldehyde

crystallised from benzene as tan green needles, m.p. 107°, yield 0.63 g (35%). IR : ν_{max} (Nujol) (cm^{-1}) : 1650, 1490, 1220 ($\text{N}^+ - \text{O}^-$), 960 ($\text{N} - \text{OH}$).

Reduction of 1-hydroxy-2-p-chlorophenyl imidazole-3-oxide (phanquone) with NaBH₄ :

To a refluxing solution of imidazole oxide (0.36 g, 0.001 mole) in absolute alcohol (10 ml) was added solid NaBH₄ (0.37 g, 0.01 mole). The colour of the mixture changes from green to red and finally to brown. Then it was refluxed for 2 hr. Solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure. The residue was treated with water, extracted with ether and the ethereal extract was dried (MgSO₄). Removal of ether gave the hydroxy imidazole, m.p. 109°, yield 0.28 g (82%).

IR : ν_{max} (KBr) (cm^{-1}) : 3280, 1580, 960 (N - OH).

Reaction of 2-p-chlorophenyl phanquimidazole with hexacyanoferrate: Isolation of dimer IX (R=p-Cl phenyl):

A cold saturated aqueous solution of hexacyanoferrate (280 ml) was added dropwise over 2 hr to a solution of the title imidazole (1.32 g, 0.0036 mole) in absolute ethanol (160 ml) containing KOH (16 g). The mixture was maintained at 5 to 10° and stirred by bubbling in a stream of oxygen. The precipitate was collected, washed thoroughly with cold water and dried. The crude product (~0.5 g) was dissolved in benzene. Trituration with petroleum spirit (b.p. 40 - 60°) afforded the dimer IX as pale orange needles, m.p. 34s°, yield 0.24 g (19%),

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